

IMPLEMENTATION OF WASH IN SCHOOLS (WINS) PROGRAM IN BAYBAY 2 DISTRICT

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Recommended Citation:

Mendez, V. (2024) Implementation of Wash in Schools (Wins) Program in Baybay 2 District. *Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception Insights*. 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13316785>.

Implementation of Wash in Schools (Wins) Program in Baybay 2 District

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the implementation of the Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) in Schools (WinS) program in the 10 schools of Baybay 2 District. Utilizing an embedded research design, the study assessed the level of implementation and extent of practice across the program's five key areas. In quantitative, data were collected using survey questionnaires among 10 school heads, 15 teachers, and 365 learners. In the treatment of data, the weighted mean was used and interpreted using a descriptive correlational analysis. The findings revealed a "high" level of implementation and a "high" extent of practice. By using a chi-square test, a highly significant relationship between these two factors was shown and aligns with the theory of change, suggesting that effective implementation leads to extensive practice. Whereas in qualitative, data were collected through interviews from three school heads, three teachers, and nine learners. In the analysis using phenomenological approach with the aid of MAXQDA software; the participants' experiences were classified into three main themes: first is Achievements with the sub-themes: Nurturing Holistic Education, Transformative Impacts, and Fostering Health and Hygiene; second is Challenges with the sub-themes: Striving for Excellence, Addressing Resource Gaps, and Building Hygienic Environment; and third is Suggestions with the sub-themes: Strategic Advancements, Empowering Well-being, and Intensifying Awareness. An action plan is the output of this study.

Keywords: *implementation, level, extent, practices, SLAC, WinS program*

Received: January 2024
Accepted: March 2024
Available: May 2024

INTRODUCTION

The Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) in Schools (WinS) program is a global initiative aimed at promoting hygiene and sanitation practices in schools, with an essential focus on improving the well-being of learners, especially girls. It advocates for the adoption of good hygiene habits like washing the hands with soap, proper menstrual hygiene management, and safe disposal of waste (UNICEF, 2018). This program also prioritizes providing schools with clean water, secure and hygienic toilets, and adequate handwashing stations (McGinnis et al., 2017). Moreover, according to Antwi-Agyei et al. (2017), several entities, including governments, NGOs, and international organizations collaborate to implement this program through partnerships involving schools, communities, and governments.

A fundamental viewpoint of hygiene practices is emphasizing proper hand hygiene. This is highlighted by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021) stating that washing the hands with soap and water is a direct yet compelling strategy to kill germs and decrease the transmission of pathogens up to 40%. Additionally, Sinika, S. K. (2018) reveals that executing handwashing conventions in schools gets to be pivotal in relieving the spread of common sicknesses like respiratory contaminations and gastrointestinal maladies. In connection, Tripathy et al. (2019) uncovers that the Comprehensive WinS Program essentially brought down the predominance of reported gastrointestinal symptoms such as diarrhea and vomiting among learners. Moreover, the intervention correlated with advancements in educational outcomes, includes increased attendance and academic performance. They conclude that a comprehensive WASH in Schools program can have substantial benefits on both learners' health and educational performance.

In affluent Asian countries, there is a strong focus on advanced infrastructure, efficient waste management systems, and elevated hygiene standards to safeguard public health and curb the transmission of diseases (Asharf & Zainabi, 2022; Okaali et al., 2022). Singapore, as highlighted by the National Environment Agency (n.d), is lauded for its exceptional sanitation practices. The country's comprehensive waste management system encompasses efficient garbage collection, recycling programs, and state-of-the-art waste-to-energy incineration plants. Public toilets in Singapore are widely recognized for their cleanliness, featuring automated systems for flushing and cleaning. The government places a significant emphasis on public education regarding hygiene practices, including regular handwashing. Similarly, the Ministry of Environment (n.d), boasts Japan's well-maintained public toilets with advanced features like bidets, self-cleaning mechanisms, and sensor-operated functions. Japan's efficient waste management system prioritizes recycling and waste separation, while public areas, schools, and workplaces are equipped with facilities promoting regular handwashing. Moreover, the Ministry of Environment (n.d) states that the Republic of Korea has a comprehensive waste management system that includes separate collections of recyclables, general waste, and food waste. Advanced technology, such as smart waste bins and automated waste collection systems, ensures efficient waste disposal. South Korea also promotes good hygiene practices through public education campaigns and the provision of clean public facilities.

In addition, Aiemjoy et al. (2020) demonstrate the viability of WASH (Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene) intercessions, such as providing secure drinking water, handwashing facilities, gender-specific toilets, and health education, in decreasing the burden of diarrheal maladies among schoolchildren in low-income settings like Ethiopia. Moreover, Bolatova et al. (2021) conclude that addressing WASH challenges in schools in rural Central Kazakhstan requires a

comprehensive approach, including infrastructure improvements, increased funding, government support, targeted instruction, and awareness-raising activities. Furthermore, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2021) notes that handwashing can decrease the risk of respiratory diseases by 16-21% and by implementing handwashing routines in schools, it can significantly diminish the rate of illnesses such as colds, flu, and gastrointestinal infections among learners and staff.

In the Philippines, DepEd Order No.56, s. 2009 mandates the quick development of water and handwashing offices in all schools for flu avoidance. It emphasizes the availability of running water and soap in all schools with the adequate facilities and if running water is not available, storage of clean water in a clean container/drum may suffice. In addition, DepEd Order No.65, s. 2009 underlies the WinS program and highlights that cleanliness insufficiencies in open schools, especially lacking water and sterile offices, can lead to lack of healthy sustenance, destitute physical development, and different illnesses. In 2016, DepEd Order No. 10 was issued, titled "Policy and Guidelines on the Comprehensive WASH in Schools (WinS) Program". It outlines an all-encompassing approach for individual health care and environmental sanitation in schools, intending to generate positive outcomes on the following key areas: water, sanitation, hygiene, health education, and deworming.

The significance of the WinS program lies in addressing the detrimental effects of inadequate sanitation facilities and poor hygiene practices on children's health, school attendance, and academic performance (UNICEF, 2018). Based on the WHO/UNICEF Joint Monitoring Programme's 2018, Global Baseline Report on Drinking Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene in Schools, around 20% of schools worldwide need basic facilities for water and sanitation, and in low-income nations, over half of all primary schools lack adequate toilets. The study also highlights that about 900 million children need access to essential basic hygiene practices at their schools.

Similarly, Ofori-Kuma et al. (2018) demonstrates that only 69% of schools around the world have essential drinking water services, 66% have basic sanitation, and only a small fraction has basic hygiene facilities. Furthermore, based from the recent findings of Udto (2022), the Philippines contains a soil-transmitted helminth disease rate of around 43.7% among preschoolers and 44.7% among school-age children. This high disease rate is related with variables such as destitution, constrained access to secure and clean water, insufficient sanitation, and destitute hygiene.

The WASH in School program was implemented in Baybay City Division in the year 2019 along with its WinS monitoring and validation that were carried out to evaluate the program's implementation. However, based on the WinS 3-star report for schools from School Year 2020 to 2021, only four schools in Baybay City Division have been validated by the regional focal persons as having earned the 3-star rank, namely Pomponan National High School, Bunga National High School, Gacat Elementary School, and Kilim Elementary School and none of these schools comes from Baybay 2 District.

As a science teacher, the researcher aimed to study the WaSH in School program to learners. The pivotal role of clean water, sanitation, and cleanliness in advancing comprehensive health, encompassing both physical well-being, such as lessening the rate of waterborne illnesses and improving nutritional status, and mental health, including aspects like cognitive development and psychological well-being. The objective was to integrate these essential concepts into the scientific curriculum through this study, thereby equipping learners with knowledge and skills that will not only enhance their overall well-being but also empower them to be responsible members of society.

Moreover, the focus of this study is on fostering an understanding of how environmental health straightforwardly impacts individual wellbeing. By giving learners with practical courses and hands-on investigations, the objective is to empower them, to impact positive change and contribute to a healthier, more sustainable future, where they understand and esteem the interconnection between environmental practices and holistic health.

Regarding the beneficiaries of this study, numerous stakeholders in the education industry can gain significantly from the implementation of the Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) in school program. First and foremost, this effort will primarily benefit learners. Their general well-being and health will benefit by having access to clean water, better sanitation frameworks, and adequate cleanliness practices in schools. Additionally, it promotes a secure and welcoming learning environment, especially for females who frequently struggle with managing menstrual hygiene. Thus, the study and implementation of the WASH in school program holds great promise for multiple beneficiaries. Learners, teachers, communities and society at large will benefit from better access to clean water, improved sanitation and the promotion of good hygiene practices in schools. By addressing these fundamental needs, the program supports better health outcomes, inclusive education, and sustainable development.

Given the circumstances, the researcher assessed the WinS program's implementation in Baybay 2 to its five key areas: water, sanitation, hygiene, health education, deworming. Furthermore, the Department of Education in Baybay City, and future researchers will benefit from the data provided in this study, the recommendations and interventions can help improve successful program implementation in the coming years.

Research Questions

This study assessed the level of implementation of the Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene in Schools (WinS) Program in Baybay 2 District. Specifically, it addressed the following questions:

1.) What is the respondents' level of implementation of the WinS Program in terms of:

1.1 Water;

1.2 Sanitation;

1.3 Hygiene;

1.4 Health Education;

1.5 Deworming?

2. What is the respondents' extent of practice on the implementation of the WinS Program in terms of:

2.1 Water;

2.2 Sanitation;

2.3 Hygiene;

2.4 Health Education;

2.5 Deworming?

3.) Is there a significant relationship between the implementation and practice of the WASH in Schools (WinS) program?

4.) What are the experiences of the participants in the implementation of the WASH in Schools (WinS) program?

5.) What can be proposed as output of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopted an Embedded Research Design, as articulated by Creswell (2020), where the quantitative aspect was primary, and the qualitative aspect was secondary. This design is particularly effective for exploring complex phenomena, because it combines diverse sorts of information to pick up a more comprehensive understanding.

The quantitative aspect of this research employed a descriptive-correlational method. This choice was influenced by the method's ability, as described by Rincon (2020), to identify and describe relationships between variables without inferring causality. In the qualitative aspect of this research, a phenomenological approach was utilized. This approach, as described by Wilson (2015), focuses on understanding and portraying individuals' lived encounters and the implications they attribute to those encounters.

The Sample and Locale of the Study

The methodology of this study was planned to comprehensively assess the implementation of the Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) in Schools (WinS) Program in Baybay 2 District. For the quantitative aspects, the study employed complete enumeration for the ten school heads in the district. Based on the Baybay 2 District data as of March 2023, the total enrollment was 2,123 learners, and there were 98 teachers as shown in Table 1. To manage this population size, cluster sampling was used. The clusters were divided into Grades one to six for elementary schools, Grades seven to ten for Junior High School, and Grades 11 to 12 for Senior High School. A basic lottery method was used to randomly select one grade level from each cluster, resulting in the selection of Grade 6 for elementary, Grade 9 for Junior High School learners, and Grade 11 for Senior High School learners. Teacher-advisers were chosen as respondents since they were the immediate contacts of these selected learners.

For the qualitative aspect, purposive sampling was applied. Participants were selected from those who answered the questionnaires, focusing on individuals who could provide in-depth information relevant to the study. The qualitative sample comprised three school heads, three teachers, and three learners from each educational level (elementary, junior high, and senior high). These participants were chosen from different schools to ensure a diverse range of

experiences and perspectives on the implementation of the WinS program. The selection of schools was primarily based on proximity to the researcher's station, but all willing informants were considered for participation in the study.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

RESPONDENTS	POPULATION	SAMPLE SIZE (quantitative)	SAMPLE SIZE (qualitative)
School Heads	10	10 ^a	3
Teachers	98	15	3
Learners	2123	365	9
Total	2231	390	15

^a -complete enumeration

Research Instrument

The study utilized a survey questionnaire as the principal instrument for gathering data. The indicators in the survey questionnaire were originally based on the Department of Education (DepEd) WinS Tool, as stated in Section 10 of DepEd Order series of 2016. These indicators were then modified and contextualized by the researcher to better suit the specific environments and needs of the schools participating in this study. This questionnaire was divided into two parts, each targeting specific aspects of the WASH in School (WinS) program in schools. Moreover, the survey instrument underwent a thorough pre-testing phase. It was reviewed for content validity by a division WinS coordinator. This was followed by a pilot test involving 30 learners, three teachers, and three school heads from a different district, further establishing the instrument's reliability and applicability. Also, to ensure the reliability of the questionnaire, Cronbach's alpha was employed. The results indicated that the survey got 0.95 which is described as "very reliable," confirming its effectiveness in measuring the constructs related to the WinS program's implementation and practices.

As to its features, it encompassed five key areas: Water (three indicators), Hygiene (13 indicators), Sanitation (16 indicators), Health Education (six indicators), and Deworming (two indicators). For Part I, it focused on evaluating the implementation level of the WASH in School program based on the achievement of criteria based on the WinS Tool to which the WinS program's key areas have been carried out in a particular school setting. Respondents rated the implementation on a Likert scale with five points, from 1 (Poorly Implemented) to 5 (Very Highly Implemented). Additionally, for Part II it evaluated the implementation of the WinS program as to the respondent's extent of practice or their actual and first-hand experiences. The responses were again rated on a scale with five points, from 1 (Poorly Practiced) to 5 (Very Highly Practiced).

Furthermore, the research integrated the qualitative component by means of open-ended interviews to obtain a more profound understanding of the WinS program's execution. A code number, date, location, duration, and classification of the participants were all included in the interview guide that was created. Additionally, it focused on the experiences of the participants with their suggestions, recommendations, and plans on how to improve the school's implementation of the program, leading to answering the fourth and fifth research questions.

Data Gathering

Before initiating data collection, necessary approvals were secured from the Graduate School Dean, the Schools Division Superintendent of Baybay City Division, the Baybay 2 District-In-Charge, and the heads of schools in the Baybay 2 District. Ethical considerations were at the forefront of this research process. Upon obtaining all necessary approvals, the researcher personally distributed the questionnaires to the participants. During this process, the researcher ensured that each participant was fully informed about the study's purpose and their rights as a participant. After the distribution, the questionnaires were retrieved, and their indicators were immediately checked for completeness and accuracy.

In treating the data for the quantitative part, the weighted mean was used in analyzing and interpreting the respondents' level of WinS implementation and extent of practice. Also, Chi-square test was employed because it examined the link between the two categorical variables – the degree of implementation and extent of practice of the WinS program under investigation. As to the qualitative part, the researcher gathered the data from the 15 participants of the interview. Moreover, with the use of MAXQDA software, themes were further examined and developed through additional analysis and comparison throughout the dataset to understand the data gathered from the open-ended interview. Furthermore, the responses to the questionnaire and interview were treated with utmost confidentiality. With that, all the data and analysis were presented using tables and figures for better visualization of the results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After Respondents' Level of Implementation of the WinS Program

Table 2.1 Respondents' Level of Implementation of the WinS Program in terms of Water

Indicators	Weighted Mean			Average	Level of Implementation
	Learners (n=365)	Teachers (n=15)	School Heads (n=10)		
1.Our school has a safe drinking water which we drink for free	3.68	4.07	3.50	3.75	High
2.Our school tested the water quality multiple times every calendar year	2.97	2.87	2.70	2.85	Moderate
3.Our school has a daily source of water for cleaning	4.33	4.40	4.50	4.41	High
Overall	3.66	3.78	3.57	3.67	High

The results indicate that the level of implementation of the WinS program in terms of water is high, with an overall average mean of 3.67. This suggests that the respondents nearly met all the 3-star requirements of the WinS program. This high level of implementation can be attributed to two indicators being rated as "high" and one as "moderate." Among the indicators rated "high," the one stating "Our school has a daily source of water for cleaning" achieved the highest mean of 4.41. This suggests that the Baybay 2 District's schools have an adequate amount of water for everyday use, particularly for cleaning the restrooms, sinks, windows,

walls, and floors. This result is in line with studies by Anand et al. (2021) showing that water is available to most schools, and Nunes et al. (2019) noting that public schools typically have sufficient water supplies for consumption.

However, the indicator "Our school tested the water quality multiple times every calendar year" received a moderate weighted mean of 2.85. This suggests that only about half of the 3-star requirements were met in this area, indicating that regular water testing is not yet a well-established practice in many schools. Such finding needs attention, as consistent water quality testing is crucial for ensuring the safety and healthiness of the school environment. Moreover, it implies that regular testing of water quality is essential to detect any contaminants and ensure that the water to be used by learners and staff is safe. Furthermore, the finding points to a broader challenge in the implementation of the WinS Program. It suggests the need for schools to place greater emphasis on this aspect, which may involve allocating more resources, enhancing staff training, or integrating more robust systems for regular water testing. This moderate mean also serves as a call to action for school administrators and program implementers to strengthen their efforts in ensuring regular water quality testing. This is consistent with the claim of Johnson et al. (2018) that there is a need for regular water quality testing in schools to ensure safe drinking water, and Razman et al. (2023), who stress the provision of water quality monitoring system in identifying contaminated water.

Table 2.2 Respondents' Level of Implementation of the WinS Program in terms of Sanitation

Indicators	Weighted Mean				Level of Implementation
	Learners (n=365)	Teachers (n=15)	School Heads (n=10)	Average	
1. Our school has a ratio of learners to toilet seats (by gender) that is 50 or fewer	3.37	3.53	3.70	3.53	High
2. Our school has toilets that are private, secure, equipped with a door and lock, with enough lighting and ventilation, and wrapping materials for used pads	4.12	4.13	4.20	4.15	High
3. Our school has soap and water available for hand washing in or near toilets	4.18	4.07	4.10	4.12	High
4. Our school has a facility for washing in female toilets for Menstrual Hygiene Management (MHM)	3.06	3.07	3.50	3.21	Moderate
5. Our school has detached toilets that are located within view of school building and people	3.56	3.60	3.20	3.45	Moderate
6. Our school has a wheelchair-accessible toilet for persons with limited mobility	3.24	3.40	3.40	3.35	Moderate
7. Our school has daily cleaning of toilets, hand washing stations and other water facilities	4.27	4.00	4.70	4.32	High
8. Our school has financing for regular support and repair of toilets, hand washing, and other water facilities that comes from the standard school budget (i.e. MOOE) and/or other DepEd funds	3.88	4.20	4.50	4.19	High
9. Our school has no burning of waste	3.76	3.60	3.40	3.59	High
10. Our school has segregated trash bins with cover that are accessible in all classrooms, toilets, canteens, workplaces, clinics, play areas, gardens, corridors, and gyms	4.58	4.67	4.40	4.55	Very High
11. Our school has comprehensive waste segregation system that is in place, such as policy, facility and practice, and sanctions for non-compliance	3.58	4.13	3.20	3.64	High

12. Our school has garbage collection at least twice a week, or has compost facility for biodegradable waste and Materials Recovery Facility (MRF) for recyclable waste	3.97	4.27	3.30	3.85	High
13. Our school has functional septic tank that is available in all toilets	4.42	4.73	4.70	4.62	Very High
14. Our school has functional drainage within the kitchen and wash areas to guarantee that there is no stagnant water within the school	4.07	4.47	4.20	4.25	High
15. Our school has a system (policy, practice, individuals, process, and structure) that is in place to guarantee that there is no stagnant water in the school	4.06	4.13	3.90	4.03	High
16. Our school has food handlers with a health certificate and a canteen with an updated sanitary permit	4.05	3.67	3.60	3.77	High
Overall	3.89	3.98	3.88	3.91	High

The data yielded an overall average rating of 3.91, which is described as “high.” This indicates that the respondents have implemented almost all the 3-star requirements of the WinS program. This high rating is attributed to two indicators being rated as “very high,” eleven as “high,” and three as “moderate.” Among these sixteen indicators, the highest mean of 4.62 is for “Our school has functional septic tank that is available in all toilets,” indicating that the schools possess proper sanitation facilities in their toilets. Additionally, the fact that the majority of respondents gave this a high rating suggests that they were aware of its existence, indicating that schools place a high value on having pleasant and clean restrooms. Thus, these results are consistent with the research of Evans et al. (2021) who state that septic tank system have a beneficial effect on the productivity of staff and learners in the school community.

The second-highest indicator, with a mean of 4.55, was “Our school has segregated trash bins with cover that are accessible in all classrooms, toilets, canteens, workplaces, clinics, play areas, gardens, corridors, and gyms.” The fact that covered garbage cans with separators are so widely available across school grounds implies that they were given priority in schools so as with the presence of three sets of waste bins, huge bins designated in specific areas of the school, and a compost pit to ensure correct garbage segregation. These all suggest that schools placed a high priority on cleanliness when it comes to proper waste disposal and is a clear indication of their commitment to comprehensive sanitation and environmental education. This is in line with the study of Dy et al. (2022), which highlights the significance of trash cans and the need to prioritize them in order to prevent the negative effects of poor waste disposal.

However, moderate implementation was observed in the indicator “Our school has a facility for washing in female toilets for Menstrual Hygiene Management (MHM),” with a mean of 3.21. This implies that not all schools provide these facilities. This suggest that despite the fact that these facilities are essential in schools, particularly for women who require a safe space during their monthly period, there is little attention given to them and little orientation on the matter. This result is consistent with the study of Kuhlmann et al. (2019), which emphasizes MHM as a developing public health and human rights concern. Similarly, the indicator “Our school has a wheelchair-accessible toilet for persons with limited mobility” received a lower mean of 3.35. This implies that most schools have inadequate facilities tailored to the needs of persons with disabilities, resonating with the findings of Afio et al. (2016), which indicated a general lack of such facilities. Additionally, “Our school has detached toilets that are located within view of school building and people” has a mean of 3.45, suggesting less provision for appropriately located facilities for human waste disposal, supported by Ngimbwa et al. (2020) who claim about the lack of detached toilets in Tanzanian schools.

The result also revealed that the learners have the highest rating in terms of the indicator “Our school has food handlers with a health certificate and a canteen with an updated sanitary permit”. This suggested that since they are the primary patrons and think the food is tasty and safe, the learners anticipate this permit to be observed in the school canteen. However, since there may not have been as much assessment of the execution of this criterion and they may not have visited the cafeteria area frequently, the teachers and school administrators may have been hesitant to choosing the highest numerical rating. Overall, the indicator was assessed as high, indicating that the Baybay 2 district's schools placed a high priority on health and cleanliness when handling and preparing food. However, there is still a need for oversight of the food cooked and the issuance of permits for each vendor in the cafeteria. Hence, these findings are connected to the study conducted by Ubane, S. C., and Pajantoy, A. J. C. (2022) arguing that although the food offered promotes the eating of wholesome meals, the marketing of unhealthy foods is only loosely regulated and requires continual support to be carried out. This is further corroborated by a study of Acilo, J. E., & Cabal, E. M. (2021), which suggests that the administration of the school canteen should push learners to purchase healthful foods and stress the need of clean food as a key component of a well-managed canteen.

Table 2.3 Respondents’ Level of Implementation of the WinS Program in terms of Hygiene

Indicators	Weighted Mean				Level of Implementation
	Learners (n=365)	Teachers (n=15)	School Heads (n=10)	Average	
1.Our school has daily supervised group hand washing with soap for all learners that is led by pupil/student leaders	3.47	3.80	3.60	3.62	High
2.Our school has standard supply of soap for handwashing	3.35	3.60	3.90	3.62	High
3.Our school has learner to group facility with soap ratio of 1:100 for one shift	3.45	3.73	4.20	3.80	High
4.Our school has individual hand washing facilities with soap in strategic areas within the school (eg. near canteen/eating zones, play areas, and toilets)	4.04	4.33	4.50	4.29	High
5.Our school has individual hand washing with soap that is done during critical times	4.01	3.93	4.00	3.98	High
6.Our school has daily supervised activity of tooth brushing with fluoride toothpaste for all learners that is led by student/pupil leaders	3.52	3.40	3.40	3.44	Moderate
7.Our school has standard supply of fluoride toothpaste for the tooth brushing activity	3.45	3.20	3.80	3.48	Moderate
8.Our school has repair and maintenance requirements that are reflected within the School Improvement Plan and Annual Improvement Plan	4.07	4.40	4.70	4.39	High
9.Our school has soap, toothbrush, and toothpaste that are given by the school through DepEd funds complemented by external stakeholders	3.82	3.73	4.60	4.05	High
10.Our school has sanitary pads that are available in the school	3.57	3.47	4.50	3.85	High
11.Our school has information on appropriate disposal of sanitary pads in the toilet of girls	3.45	4.00	3.80	3.75	High
12.Our school has DepEd approved Information, Education and Communication (IEC) materials on	3.49	3.67	4.30	3.82	High

menstrual hygiene management for teachers and learners					
13.Our school has a rest space/ changing room for MHM that is secure and comfortable (not necessarily within the CR)	2.84	3.13	4.40	3.46	Moderate
Overall	3.58	3.72	4.13	3.81	High

The data reveal that the overall average mean of the respondents' level of implementation in terms of hygiene was "high," with a mean of 3.81. This suggests that the respondents nearly fulfilled all the 3-star requirements of the WinS program. This high average was primarily due to ten out of thirteen hygiene indicators receiving "high" ratings, while the remaining three were rated as "moderate." One of the standout indicators, "Our school has repair and maintenance requirements that are reflected within the School Improvement Plan and Annual Improvement Plan (AIP)," achieved the highest mean of 4.39. This high mean indicates a growing use of these plans to structure and monitor hygiene implementation goals in schools and yet this result supported the findings of Redding et al. (2020) that such planning tools are instrumental in facilitating ambitious school improvements. However, the indicator "Our school has daily supervised activity of tooth brushing with fluoride toothpaste for all learners that is led by student/pupil leaders" received a "moderate" rating, with a mean of 3.44. This suggests that the activity of toothbrushing was less frequently supervised and led in schools. This matter should be given priority in schools as highlighted by Perez et al. (2023) that there is a need for enhanced focus on this aspect of oral hygiene, which is crucial for maintaining dental health and preventing oral diseases.

Another notable finding was the "moderate" level of implementation for the indicator "Our school has a rest space/ changing room for MHM that is secure and comfortable (not necessarily within the CR)." The mean rating for this indicator, especially from the student respondents, was relatively low at 2.84. This suggests that many learners, particularly the main beneficiaries of this facility, were not fully aware of or did not have access to these MHM spaces. In contrast, the data indicated that school heads and teachers were aware of the existence of these facilities however they may not have effectively communicated their availability to learners or properly labeled them. This result is in line with the findings of Johnson et al. (2018) who emphasize the need to prioritize MHM in schools, recognizing it as a crucial aspect of public health and gender equality.

Table 2.4 Respondents' Level of Implementation of the WinS Program in terms of Health Education

Indicators	Weighted Mean			Average	Level of Implementation
	Learners (n=365)	Teachers (n=15)	School Heads (n=10)		
1.Our school has IEC materials that are available in classrooms and strategic places (eg. canteen, play areas, toilets, hand washing facilities, etc.)	3.24	3.27	3.80	3.43	Moderate
2.Our school has organized teams and accountable units to promote WASH in Schools (WinS) (e.g. Technical Working Groups (TWGs), student clubs)	3.92	3.87	4.30	4.03	High

3.Our school has WinS as part of In-Service Training (INSET) for teachers	3.61	4.07	4.00	3.89	High
4.Our school has available WinS learning/ instructional materials in support of teaching WinS in the K to 12 curriculum	3.51	3.80	4.30	3.87	High
5.Our school has planned and organized activities for parents/stakeholders for learning and advocating WinS	3.73	3.73	4.00	3.82	High
6.Our school has WinS as part of the extra-curricular program of learners	3.82	4.00	3.90	3.91	High
Overall	3.64	3.79	4.05	3.83	High

The results of the study indicate that the level of implementation in health education within the WinS program is "high," with an overall weighted mean of 3.83. This high rating suggests that the respondents successfully met nearly all the 3-star requirements of the program. The rating is based on five indicators being classified as "high" and one as "moderate" in their level of implementation. Among the indicators rated as "high," the one stating "Our school has organized teams and accountable units to promote WASH in Schools (WinS) (e.g., Technical Working Groups (TWGs), student clubs)" achieved the highest average of 4.03. This indicates that the majority of schools have effectively established teams or units dedicated to advocating the WinS program, aligning with UNESCO (2021) recommendation for concerted efforts in the WinS initiatives. Nevertheless, the indicator "Our school has IEC materials that are available in classrooms and strategic places (e.g., canteen, play areas, toilets, hand washing facilities, etc.)" received a "moderate" rating, with the lowest mean of 3.43. This implies that there is a need for more widespread dissemination of Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) resources throughout the school to advocate the importance of the WinS program. This finding resonates with Halliday (2020) who highlights IEC as an effective approach for addressing a range of health-related issues.

It should be noted that the study revealed a disparity in the means on implementation among different respondent groups categorized as high. School heads had the highest level of implementation in health education with a mean of 4.05, followed by teachers with a mean of 3.79, and then learners with a mean of 3.64. This discrepancy indicates a gap in implementation between school administration and the primary beneficiaries, the learners which may mean that school heads are well-informed about health education indicators, and more effort should be exerted on this area for improved implementation and information dissemination. Hence, this relates to the findings of Paulus et al. (2020) that due to the evolving roles of school heads, challenges in monitoring and disseminating information about the different school programs arise. For teachers, the results imply a solid understanding and implementation of health education, as they are the implementers. This is supported by Psarouli et al. (2022) that teachers are crucial in implementing health education programs. Furthermore, Bezeau et al. (2020) notes that incorporating health education into teaching practices is a gradual process that demands time and effort. The data for learners suggests a lower level of awareness or observation of health education implementation may be because there was a lack of integrating this in the daily lesson. Hence, this aligns with the findings of CDC (2017) that many schools are placing a low priority on implementing health education.

Table 2.5 Respondents' Level of Implementation of the WinS Program in terms of Deworming

Indicators	Weighted Mean			Average	Level of Implementation
	Learners (n=365)	Teachers (n=15)	School Heads (n=10)		
1. Our school has deworming that is done semi-annually, in the presence of a health personnel, in coordination with DOH, and with parent's consent	4.22	4.53	4.30	4.35	High
2. Our school has at least 85% of school learners that were dewormed	3.94	4.20	4.20	4.11	High
Overall	4.08	4.37	4.20	4.22	High

The study's results show that the level of implementation for deworming within the WinS program is classified as "high," with an impressive overall average of 4.22. This high rating suggests that the respondents have successfully implemented almost all the 3-star requirements of the WinS program in this regard. Particularly noteworthy is the indicator "Our school has deworming that is done semi-annually, in the presence of health personnel, in coordination with the Department of Health (DOH), and with parental consent," which got the highest mean of 4.35. This high mean highlights the success of the school's deworming programs and suggests that the school places a high priority on preventing soil-transmitted helminth (STH) infections, which can result in a large number of absences if neglected. Thus, this is corroborated by Ali et al. (2019), who stress the significance of deworming programs conducted in schools, as Anderson, K. L. (2020) states that school-based deworming initiatives improve learners' health.

However, the indicator "Our school has at least 85% of school learners that were dewormed" showed a slightly lower average of 4.11. Despite both indicators being rated as "high," this reveals a gap, particularly in the learners' data, which had a mean of 3.94. This gap might suggest that a portion of the student population either lacks awareness of the deworming activities conducted at school or did not participate in them and the COVID-19 pandemic's impact on school operations might have contributed to this discrepancy. This finding is congruent with the study of Kabore et al. (2021) who claim that the closure of schools during the pandemic hindered the continuation of deworming programs in some regions. Furthermore, according to the WinS coordinators, there was a lack of thorough monitoring of the distribution of deworming tablets by barangay health workers (BHWs) during this period.

Extent of Practice in the Implementation of the WinS Program

Table 3.1 Respondents' Extent of Practice in the Implementation of the WinS Program in terms of Water

Indicators	Weighted Mean			Average	Extent of Practice
	Learners (n=365)	Teachers (n=15)	School Heads (n=10)		
1.Our school has a safe drinking water which we drink for free	3.65	4.00	3.80	3.82	Highly Practiced
2.Our school tested the water quality multiple times every calendar year	3.09	3.00	3.20	3.10	Moderately Practiced
3.Our school has a daily source of water for cleaning	4.21	4.40	4.40	4.34	Highly Practiced
Overall	3.65	3.80	3.80	3.75	Highly Practiced

The study reveals that the extent of practice regarding water management in the WinS program is classified as "highly practiced," with an overall average of 3.75. This indicates that the school heads, teachers, and learners, consistently engaged in practices related to water management within the program. This high level of practice is primarily due to two indicators being rated as "highly practiced" and one as "moderately practiced." Furthermore, the result supports the respondents' claim of highly implemented water management practices, demonstrating a strong correlation between the implementation and the actual practice of these measures within the schools. This alignment indicates that the schools are not only committed to setting up water management systems but are also actively ensuring their consistent use and maintenance.

The indicator "Our school has a daily source of water for cleaning" received the highest mean of 4.34, indicating that this practice is widespread and well-established in the schools of Baybay 2 district. This finding suggests that the schools have effectively implemented practices ensuring accessible water for cleaning, a crucial aspect of maintaining hygiene and health in educational environments. This is supported with the findings of Nurfadilah et al. (2018), who observed the significant role of water availability in cleaning practices within schools in India, though they noted varying levels of implementation. Conversely, the indicator "Our school tested the water quality multiple times every calendar year" got a lower weighted mean of 3.10, categorized as "moderately practiced." This indicates that while there is some level of engagement in water quality testing, it is not as consistent or widespread as other water-related practices. Ensuring safe drinking water in schools requires routine water testing, as noted by Johnson et al. (2018).

Table 3.2 Respondents' Extent of Practice in the Implementation of the WinS Program in terms of Sanitation

Indicators	Weighted Mean			Average	Extent of Practice
	Learners (n=365)	Teachers (n=15)	School Heads (n=10)		
1.Our school has a ratio of learners to toilet seats (by gender) that is 50 or fewer	3.32	3.40	3.40	3.37	Moderately Practiced
2.Our school has toilets that are private, secure, equipped with a door and lock, with enough	3.98	4.27	4.20	4.15	Highly Practiced

lighting and ventilation, and wrapping materials for used pads					
3.Our school has soap and water available for hand washing in or near toilets	4.13	4.07	4.30	4.17	Highly Practiced
4.Our school has a facility for washing in female toilets for Menstrual Hygiene Management (MHM)	3.15	3.27	3.70	3.37	Moderately Practiced
5.Our school has detached toilets that are located within view of school building and people	3.54	3.47	3.30	3.43	Moderately Practiced
6.Our school has a wheelchair-accessible toilet for persons with limited mobility	3.33	3.33	3.70	3.46	Moderately Practiced
7.Our school has daily cleaning of toilets, hand washing stations and other water facilities	4.01	4.00	4.50	4.17	Highly Practiced
8.Our school has financing for regular support and repair of toilets, hand washing, and other water facilities that comes from the standard school budget (i.e. MOOE) and/or other DepEd funds	3.73	3.87	4.30	3.97	Highly Practiced
9 Our school has no burning of waste	3.77	3.53	3.40	3.57	Highly Practiced
10.Our school has segregated trash bins with cover that are accessible in all classrooms, toilets, canteens, workplaces, clinics, play areas, gardens, corridors, and gyms	4.34	4.60	4.40	4.45	Highly Practiced
11.Our school has comprehensive waste segregation system that is in place, such as policy, facility and practice, and sanctions for non-compliance	3.41	4.07	3.40	3.63	Highly Practiced
12.Our school has garbage collection at least twice a week, or has compost facility for biodegradable waste and Materials Recovery Facility (MRF) for recyclable waste	3.79	4.33	3.60	3.91	Highly Practiced
13.Our school has functional septic tank that is available in all toilets	4.42	4.60	4.70	4.57	Very Highly Practiced
14.Our school has functional drainage within the kitchen and wash areas to guarantee that there is no stagnant water within the school	3.94	4.47	4.30	4.24	Highly Practiced
15.Our school has a system (policy, practice, individuals, process, and structure) that is in place to guarantee that there is no stagnant water in the school	4.09	4.40	4.20	4.23	Highly Practiced
16.Our school has food handlers with a health certificate and a canteen with an updated sanitary permit	3.52	3.73	3.00	3.42	Moderately Practiced
Overall	3.78	3.96	3.90	3.88	Highly Practiced

The data highlight that the respondents' extent of practice in sanitation within the WinS program is rated as "highly practiced", evidenced by an overall average of 3.88. This signifies that the respondents frequently engaged in sanitation practices as part of the WinS program. This high level of practice can be attributed to the distribution of ratings across the indicators: five were rated as "moderately practiced," ten as "highly practiced," and one as "very highly practiced." Among these indicators, the highest mean of 4.57 was recorded for "Our school has functional septic tank that is available in all toilets," categorized as "very highly practiced." This suggests that the presence and maintenance of septic tanks in schools are prioritized and well-managed, aligning with their high implementation mean. It also indicates the importance of functional septic tanks in schools ensuring proper sanitation following the guidelines by the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF, 2020) on WASH in schools. These guidelines emphasize maintaining hygiene standards, effective waste management systems, that is essential for the health and well-being of learners. Thus, the provision of this facility contributes to a safer and more hygienic learning environment.

Conversely, the indicator "Our school has a facility for washing in female toilets for Menstrual Hygiene Management (MHM)" had a moderate mean of 3.37. This suggests that while MHM facilities exist, their usage may not be as widespread or effective as other sanitation practices. This finding is reflective of the challenges highlighted in the literature regarding the adequacy and accessibility of MHM facilities in schools, as discussed in Sommer et al. (2015), which underscores the need for improved MHM facilities in educational settings.

Similarly, "Our school has a ratio of learners to toilet seats (by gender) that is 50 or fewer" also had a moderate mean of 3.37, despite being rated highly in terms of implementation might indicate underlying challenges in the accessibility or adequacy of toilet facilities in schools. This gap between the implementation of having toilets and the actual functionality and accessibility of these facilities can have significant implications. For instance, a lack of adequate toilets can lead to overcrowding, reduced privacy, and hygiene issues, which are particularly problematic for female learners. This situation can discourage toilet use, especially during menstruation, and can lead to absenteeism and reduced participation in school activities. This situation resonates with the findings of UNICEF (2018) that there is shortage of functional restrooms in educational environments and suggest the upgrading of infrastructure to create accessible and productive learning environments for everyone and aligns with the broader goals of the WinS program.

However, the indicator "Our school has food handlers that have a health certificate and a canteen with an updated sanitary permit" presented a discrepancy, being rated "moderately practiced" despite a high implementation mean. This could imply a gap in the consistent application of these standards, possibly due to a lack of monitoring and evaluation, which is significant as emphasized by Fung et al. (2018), who claim the necessity of sanitary permits for food safety. The indicator "Our school has segregated trash bins with covers that are available in all classrooms, toilets, canteens, offices, clinics, play areas, gardens, corridors, and gyms" was rated as "highly practiced," showing only a slight deviation from its "very high" implementation level. This small difference may indicate some gaps in the availability or use of segregated trash bins, hence in line with the findings of Mugambe et al. (2022), who highlighted similar challenges in waste segregation in institutional settings.

Table 3.3 Respondents' Extent of Practice in the Implementation of the WinS Program in terms of Hygiene

Indicators	Weighted Mean				Extent of Practice
	Learners (n=365)	Teachers (n=15)	School Heads (n=10)	Average	
1. Our school has daily supervised group hand washing with soap for all learners that is led by pupil/student leaders	3.47	4.00	3.80	3.76	Highly Practiced
2. Our school has standard supply of soap for handwashing	3.46	3.87	4.00	3.77	Highly Practiced
3. Our school has learner to group facility with soap ratio of 1:100 for one shift	3.51	4.13	4.30	3.98	Highly Practiced
4. Our school has individual hand washing facilities with soap in strategic areas within the school (eg. near canteen/eating zones, play areas, and toilets)	3.87	4.07	4.50	4.15	Highly Practiced
5. Our school has individual hand washing with soap that is done during critical times	3.96	4.00	4.10	4.02	Highly Practiced

6.Our school has daily supervised activity of tooth brushing with fluoride toothpaste for all learners that is led by student/pupil leaders	3.64	3.40	4.00	3.68	Highly Practiced
7.Our school has standard supply of fluoride toothpaste for the tooth brushing activity	3.69	3.60	4.10	3.80	Highly Practiced
8.Our school has repair and maintenance requirements that are reflected within the School Improvement Plan and Annual Improvement Plan	3.99	4.33	4.70	4.34	Highly Practiced
9.Our school has soap, toothbrush, and toothpaste that are given by the school through DepEd funds complemented by external stakeholders	3.82	3.73	4.30	3.95	Highly Practiced
10.Our school has sanitary pads that are available in the school	3.87	3.93	4.30	4.04	Highly Practiced
11.Our school has information on appropriate disposal of sanitary pads in the toilet of girls	3.58	3.87	3.50	3.65	Highly Practiced
12.Our school has DepEd approved Information, Education and Communication (IEC) materials on menstrual hygiene management for teachers and learners	3.38	3.67	4.10	3.72	Highly Practiced
13.Our school has a rest space/ changing room for MHM that is secure and comfortable (not necessarily within the CR)	2.86	3.47	4.20	3.51	Highly Practiced
Overall	3.62	3.85	4.11	3.86	Highly Practiced

The findings of the study indicate that the extent of practice in hygiene under the WinS program is rated as "highly practiced," with an overall mean of 3.86. This high mean reflects the respondents' frequent engagement in hygiene practices as part of the WinS program. This result is in line with Brewer et al. (2019) which emphasize the critical aspect of hygiene in promoting health and preventing disease spread in school settings. Among the various indicators, "Our school has repair and maintenance requirements that are reflected within the School Improvement Plan and Annual Improvement Plan" received the highest mean of 4.34. This suggests a strong emphasis on maintaining hygiene facilities, that is supported by the findings of Guzman J. (2022), who notes the positive effect of such maintenance on the academic performance of learners. Effective maintenance of hygiene facilities is essential in creating a conducive learning environment and is supported by the guidelines of the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2020) on maintaining healthy school environments.

The lower score of 3.51 for the indicator "Our school has a rest space/ changing room for MHM that is secure and comfortable (not necessarily within the CR)," particularly noted among student respondents, suggests several underlying reasons why teachers, learners, and school heads may perceive these facilities differently. School heads and teachers may have a higher rating for this indicator due to their awareness of the policy requirements and a prioritization of meeting these standards. They might recognize the importance of MHM facilities from an administrative and compliance perspective, leading to a more favorable assessment of their availability and quality. In contrast, the lower rating from learners, especially female learners who are the primary users of these facilities, indicate a gap between the availability of MHM facilities and their actual usability or accessibility. Learners are likely to rate these facilities based on their direct experiences, which might include issues such as inadequate privacy, insufficient maintenance, or limited access during school hours.

Table 3.4 Respondents’ Extent of Practice in the Implementation of the WinS Program in terms of Health Education

Indicators	Weighted Mean			Average	Extent of Practice
	Learners (n=365)	Teachers (n=15)	School Heads (n=10)		
1.Our school has IEC materials that are present in classrooms and strategic places (eg. canteen, play areas, toilets, hand washing facilities, etc.)	3.22	3.40	3.80	3.47	Moderately Practiced
2.Our school has organized teams and accountable units to promote WASH in Schools (WinS) (e.g. Technical Working Groups (TWGs), student clubs)	3.84	3.93	4.30	4.02	Highly Practiced
3.Our school has WinS as part of In-Service Training (INSET) for teachers	3.61	4.07	4.20	3.96	Highly Practiced
4.Our school has available WinS learning/ instructional materials in support of teaching WinS in the K to 12 curriculum	3.44	3.87	4.30	3.87	Highly Practiced
5.Our school has planned and organized activities for parents/stakeholders for learning and advocating WinS	3.68	3.73	4.00	3.80	Highly Practiced
6.Our school has WinS as part of the extra-curricular program of learners	3.81	4.00	4.20	4.00	Highly Practiced
Overall	3.60	3.83	4.13	3.85	Highly Practiced

In terms of health education, it is rated as "highly practiced," with an overall average of 3.85, and these are supported by several studies. For instance, Seong and Yi (2021) discuss the development and effect of a pre-educational program for pre-health education public teachers' school health practice, highlighting the importance of structured health education programs in schools. Similarly, Kwon et al. (2022) highlight the significance of health education practices in educational contexts as they investigate the impacts of community health nursing in-school practice education on self-directed learning, core nursing competency, and infection control awareness of nursing school learners. These studies collectively support the importance of health education practices in schools, this aligns with the high rating in the WinS program implementation.

The indicator “Our school has organized teams and accountable units to promote WASH in Schools (WinS) (e.g., Technical Working Groups (TWGs), student clubs)” achieve the highest mean of 4.02, categorized as “highly practiced,” mirrors the active engagement and structured organization within schools to strengthen advocacy for health education. This approach aligns with UNESCO (2021) which focus on the role of Health Promoting Schools and the collective

responsibility to foster health education through collaborative efforts. The effectiveness of such organized teams in schools is supported by Goheco et al. (2022), who claim that holistic and sustainable approach to WASH that includes education, community involvement, and long-term planning. These studies underscore the importance of collaborative and structured approaches in promoting health education. Therefore, when schools establish dedicated teams or groups focused on health initiatives, there is a greater likelihood of successful implementation and sustained impact of these programs.

The indicator "Our school has IEC materials that are available in classrooms and strategic places (e.g., canteen, play areas, toilets, hand washing facilities, etc.)" receiving a lower mean of 3.47, categorized as "moderately practiced," highlights a significant area for improvement in the distribution and utilization of Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) materials within schools. This moderate rating suggests that while IEC materials may be present, their reach and effectiveness might not be fully optimized across the school environment. The need for more extensive action to improve the practice of disseminating and utilizing these IEC materials is evident. Halliday (2020) underscores the importance of this, pointing out the effectiveness of IEC materials in addressing a broad spectrum of health-related issues in educational settings and that well-designed and strategically placed IEC materials can significantly enhance learners' and staff's awareness and understanding of health practices, thereby contributing to better health outcomes. Therefore, schools should focus on not only ensuring the availability of IEC materials but also on their strategic placement, relevance, and accessibility to effectively communicate key health messages and promote healthier behaviors among the school community.

In essence, this result suggests that the effectiveness of the WinS program's implementation has a direct impact on the consistency of its practices. The differences in scores among school heads, teachers, and learners provide valuable insights into each group's perception of the program's effectiveness, highlighting areas for improvement to ensure that the program achieves its objectives for the entire school community. These results emphasize how crucial it is to conduct routine evaluations, distribute instructional materials efficiently, and implement well-structured health awareness programs in schools in order to guarantee the success of health education projects. This is essential for the immediate advantages to learners' health as well as for the more general objective supported by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2020) in their guidelines for school health programs of creating a health-conscious and knowledgeable school community.

Table 3.5 Respondents' Extent of Practice in the Implementation of the WinS Program in terms of Deworming

Indicators	Weighted Mean			Average	Extent of Practice
	Learners (n=365)	Teachers (n=15)	School Heads (n=10)		
1.Our school has deworming that is done semi-annually, in the presence of a health personnel, in coordination with DOH, and with parent's consent	4.27	4.47	4.30	4.35	Highly Practiced
2.Our school has at least 85% of school learners that were dewormed	3.93	4.13	4.20	4.09	Highly Practiced

Overall	4.10	4.3	4.25	4.22	Highly Practiced
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The results from the study indicating a "highly practiced" rating for the Extent of Practice in the Implementation of the WinS Program in terms of Deworming, with an overall average of 4.22 are supported by several studies in the field. One of this is Musuva et al. (2017), who discuss about how a school-based deworming program along the Kenyan coast used mass medicine administration for soil-transmitted helminths among preschool-aged children. Their results demonstrate the value of routine deworming procedures as well as the efficacy of such programs in educational settings. In a similar vein, Rwamwejo et al. (2023) assess the perspectives, behaviors, knowledge, and attitudes of those involved in the deworming program in rural Rwanda, providing insights into the active and regular engagement in deworming practices as part of comprehensive health programs in schools. These studies collectively reinforce the importance of deworming practices in schools, this aligns with the high rating in the WinS program implementation. Among the evaluated indicators, "Our school has deworming that is done semi-annually, in the presence of health personnel, in coordination with the Department of Health (DOH), and with parental consent," received the highest mean of 4.35. This underscores the effectiveness and regularity of deworming initiatives in schools. However, the indicator "Our school has at least 85% of school learners that were dewormed" achieved a mean of 4.09. These findings are consistent with the high level of implementation reported in Part I of the study, reflecting a comprehensive approach to deworming practices within the schools.

The high level of practice observed in this study, with an impressive overall average of 4.22 for deworming practices, demonstrates a robust commitment to addressing health issues that can significantly impact learners' well-being and academic performance. This commitment is in line with the broader public health goals advocated by organizations like the WHO (2021) and UNICEF (2020), as part of their global health initiatives. This observation is further supported by Ali et al. (2019) which reveal that school-based deworming programs has a critical role in enhancing children's health and educational outcomes and highlights improved nutritional status, reduced absenteeism, and better cognitive function among learners. These benefits are particularly significant in regions where parasitic infections are prevalent, underscoring the importance of such health interventions in the educational setting. Together, these studies corroborate the findings of the current study in Baybay 2 District, illustrating the highly implemented deworming practices on student health. The high level of practice in deworming, as observed in this study, reflects a successful alignment with international health standards and recommendations, showcasing the effectiveness of the WinS program in promoting student health.

Relationship between the Implementation and Practice of the WinS Program

Table 4 in the study provides a comprehensive summary of the significant relationships identified between the respondents' implementation levels and their practices within the WinS program.

Table 4. Relationship between Implementation and Practice of the WinS Program

Key Areas	Chi-Square Value	Df	p-Value	Contingency Coefficient	Significance
Water	86.788	12	.000	0.427	Highly Significant
Sanitation	131.665	12	.000	0.502	Highly Significant
Hygiene	88.146	12	.000	0.429	Highly Significant
Health Education	99.805	12	.000	0.451	Highly Significant
Deworming	87.569	12	.000	0.428	Highly Significant

The analysis of the data shows a "highly significant" relationship between the level of implementation and the extent of practice across each key area of the WinS program. This significant relationship is evidenced by p-values of .000 which is less than 0.05, indicating a statistically significant link between these variables. These findings show that the effectiveness of the WinS program's implementation in Baybay 2 District has a direct and significant impact on how frequently and effectively the program's practices were carried out. This relationship aligns with the research of Lyon et al. (2018), who stressed the significance of assessing implementation as to its practice in organizational settings. Furthermore, programs with high-quality implementation are more likely to achieve their goals effectively, while poor or mediocre implementation can lead to less significant results or failure to meet objectives. This result underscores the importance of not only implementing WinS programs but also ensuring they are carried out with a high level of quality and fidelity.

Experiences in the Implementation of WinS Program

Figure 1. Single Case Model (Code Hierarchy) on School Heads Experiences on WinS Implementation

Nurturing Holistic Education. The participants expressed the instrumental role of the WinS program in nurturing holistic education. The program is seen as a critical component in addressing various aspects of learners' well-being and contributing to a comprehensive educational experience. The experiences are in line with the findings of Global Handwashing Partnership (2021) which state that collaborative effort ensures the sustainability of a program and creates a shared responsibility for the well-being of learners. This is also supported with the findings of World Bank (2019) and Smith et al. (2019) that external support is significant in program implementation across different sectors. Moreover, another study aligns seamlessly with the theme, one of these is the principles of holistic education, recognizing the interconnection between a healthy and hygienic environment and effective learning outcomes by (Freeman, Williamson, & Hyder, 2017). Similarly, Simiyu, S. (2022) emphasizes the effectiveness of creative hygiene interventions in influencing student's behavior and that provision and monitoring of facilities ensures positive impacts in nurturing the implementation of WinS program (WHO, 2019).

Striving for Excellence The participants unveiled challenges that needs to be faced with resilience and determination in order to implement an effective Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene in School (WASH) program. These challenges include financial constraints especially in a multi-grade setting which emphasize the school's resilience in prioritizing the academic needs of learners, albeit at the expense of the WinS program. The statements are in line with the study of Johnson, et al. (2020) who states that financial constraints are associated with implementing the WASH in School program including the funding of sources, budget allocation, and financial sustainability in various school settings. Whereas, Shrestha et al. (2019) emphasize that financial constraints can hinder the timely completion of required facilities, leading to compromised hygiene practices and an increased risk of waterborne diseases among students. Moreover, Kumwenda (2019) highlights that lack of clean and well-maintained spaces with proper sanitation measures is a huge challenge in implementing the WASH in School program in many schools. Furthermore, Adams et al. (2017) state that implementing a program is usually hindered by heavy workload of multi-grade teachers that is evident in educational settings where teachers are responsible for teaching students across multiple grade levels in rural school settings.

Strategic Advancements. The participants focused on strategic planning and enhancements to elevate the success of the school health initiative and emphasizing the need for additional resources, community involvement, and sustainable practices. With these, they suggested a strategic approach to resource planning, emphasizing the need to allocate resources effectively to fulfill program requirements because they recognize the importance of completing essential components of the WinS Program like clinics and regular water testing for an effective learning to happen. The statements are in line with the study of Brown et al. (2019) which notes the importance of infrastructure development in WASH programs for enhancing the overall learning environment and promoting student well-being. Moreover, the insights provided by Freeman et al. (2017) underscore the significance of community engagement in educational initiatives. Another study by Patel and Mehta (2018) highlights the profound impact of effective hygiene education on students' health behaviors and attitudes. Additionally, Smith et al. (2018) state that a school must regularly practice the needed requirements of a program and should be supervised as to its project performance, efficiency, and the achievement of the program's initiatives.

Figure 2. Single Case Model (Code Hierarchy) on Teachers Experiences on WinS Implementation

Transformative Impacts. The participants revealed the remarkable transformative impacts of the WinS Program, underscoring a collective commitment to cultivate an immaculate, secure, and health-conscious learning environment. The journey towards transformation encompasses the establishment of sustainable WASH facilities, emphasizing not only cleanliness but also prioritizing health and infusing joyful hygiene practices into the fabric of daily school life. The statements are consistent with the study of Johnson et al. (2021) which states that facilities are crucial in various contexts since it has positive impact on service quality, efficiency, and long-term sustainability of a program that do not just led to visible improvements in hygiene practices but also spurred collaborative efforts to create a clean, safe, and health-focused learning space. In connection, the provision of sufficient clean water supply, functional toilets, and additional facilities like wash stands contributes to the creation of a comprehensive WASH infrastructure and ensures personal responsibility and accessibility to health essentials (Freeman, Williamson, & Hyder, 2017). Another study by Johnson et al. (2020) emphasize the balancing aspects of education with hygiene and life-long health that is important due to its critical role in disease prevention and better public health. The study also highlights the unwavering dedication of schools in committing to create an atmosphere conducive to excellence in hygiene, health, and academic pursuits for the transformative development of every learner.

Addressing Resource Gaps. The participants emphasized the critical need for support, particularly in terms of addressing resource gaps within the educational system, to guarantee the effective implementation of the WASH in school program. By acknowledging the existing gaps and emphasizing the importance of financial support, it aims to draw attention to the essential role that adequate resources play in nurturing educational excellence. These experiences are in accordance to the findings of World Bank (2019), that resource limitations can hinder the operation of effective WASH in school program, impacting infrastructure and services in schools. This is also in line with the study of Smith et al. (2019) which states that challenges, setbacks, and potential solutions are associated with insufficient financial resources for program execution. Moreover, UNESCO (2017) and UNICEF (2017) emphasize that the lack of support, especially in terms of financial resources, poses a considerable barrier to successful hygiene and sanitation programs in schools.

Empowering Well-being. The participants emphasize the significance of an empowering approach to education, recognizing the importance of not only academic excellence but also

the integration of hygienic behaviors and life-long health encompassing initiatives that aim to enhance the overall well-being like health, safety, and quality of living for learners and the whole school. With these, they highlight concern for the safety of the water supply and recommended regular water testing to ensure ongoing monitoring and verification of water quality. These experiences are supported by the study of Smith et al. (2018) who conclude that regular water testing ensures public health, and environmental protection. Moreover, Johnson and Anderson (2019) affirm the significance of infrastructure enhancements in the success of WASH programs in schools. Similarly, dedicated funding in maintaining school-based health programs is significant as highlighted by the findings of Harris et al. (2020). Furthermore, Thompson and Gulliver (2021) note that expert-led training significantly boosts the effectiveness of advocating health awareness programs in schools.

Figure 3. Single Case Model (Code Hierarchy) on Learners Experiences on WinS Implementation

Fostering Health and Hygiene. The participants expressed the beneficial outcomes of the WinS Program on the health and hygiene practices of learners across different levels. By fostering these practices and through shared experiences, the program not only promotes individual health but also contributes in the making of a conducive and healthy school environment. These experiences are in line with the study of Johnson et al. (2021) who recognize the importance of maintaining proper hygiene for overall well-being. It also highlights the program's effectiveness in making hygiene practices enjoyable and engaging for learners, reinforcing the idea that learning about health can be a positive and communal experience. Furthermore, Smith et al. (2019) claim that improved facilities is a good indication of conduciveness in a learning environment and revealed that learners felt safe and secure in a school when provision of facilities like gender-specific toilets is prioritized. Additionally, these experiences align with global efforts to integrate health education into school curricula, recognizing the pivotal role schools play in shaping lifelong health behaviors (Freeman, Williamson, & Hyder, 2017).

Building Hygienic Environment. The participants reflected the pressing need to prioritize building a hygienic and safe school community. Several challenges, ranging from unsafe drinking water to inadequate handwashing practices, hinder the effectiveness of our current initiatives. These experiences are in relation to the findings of UNICEF (2017) which highlights the significance of safe water access in schools for promoting hygiene and preventing waterborne diseases. In addition, the World Health Organization (2019) emphasize that handwashing is a fundamental practice to prevent the spread of diseases in school settings. Hence, Global Handwashing Partnership (2019) call for continuous efforts to improve hygiene programs and address challenges faced in implementation. Furthermore, Freeman et al. (2017) state that there is a need for targeted strategies to address learner resistance in the process of implementing the program in schools. Additionally, UNESCO (2017) emphasizes the importance of gender-sensitive facilities, including separate and adequate toilets for girls, to address menstrual hygiene needs in schools.

Intensifying Awareness. The participants focused on intensified efforts made to increase awareness and understanding among stakeholders about the importance of proper WASH practices in the school environment and encompasses various aspects that contribute to raising awareness and fostering a culture of hygiene and cleanliness within the school community. These experiences align with the findings of Wilson et al. (2018), who assert that availability of the basic WinS facilities is a crucial factor influencing students' health and their engagement in educational activities. This conforms to the study of Johnson et al. (2021) that providing information and instruction to individuals and communities promotes overall health. Similarly, this is supported by Green et al. (2020) who highlights the benefits of structured health initiatives, noting that regular and well-planned health programs in schools are more likely to lead to improved health outcomes and increased student participation

CONCLUSION

Conclusion

The implications of these findings are profound. They underscore the need for a concerted effort to address the gaps in program implementation and practice. By doing so, schools can transform into WinS champions, not just within their own premises but also in the broader community. This transformation is essential for fostering a culture of health and hygiene that extends beyond the confines of the school, contributing to the well-being of the entire community. The study's results, therefore, serve as a call to action for schools, educators, and policymakers to collaboratively work towards enhancing the effectiveness of the WinS program, thereby ensuring a healthier, more educated, and more sustainable future for learners and the community at large.

Recommendations

1. Mobilize School Income-Generating Programs. Schools should actively engage in income-generating activities to ensure the timely provision of resources essential for the WinS program.

2. Develop a Contextualized Monitoring Tool. Each school should create this for easier monitoring of key indicators and achieve the 3-stars rank of the WinS program. This tool should include parameters for regular water testing, ensuring the availability of rest spaces for Menstrual Hygiene Management (MHM), verifying the sanitary permits of food handlers, providing Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) materials, and overseeing the conduct of deworming activities since based on the results these are the indicators which has lower ratings.
3. Strengthen Linkages among All Stakeholders. Each school should collaborate with external and internal stakeholders for more resource availability.
4. Adopt the Proposed Plan. Each school should focus on the conduct of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) Plan on WinS Program.

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